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EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF MGSO₄ AS ADJUVANT TO LOCAL ANAESTHETIC AGENT IN ANATOMICAL LANDMARK GUIDED TAP BLOCK FOR PERIOPERATIVE ANAESTHESIA & ANALGESIA IN UNILATERAL OPEN HERNIA REPAIR

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ABSTRACT:

BACKGROUND:

Geriatric patients of open hernia repair have comorbidities. Impaired cardiopulmonary reserves. ultrasound guided regional blocks nowadays very popular.

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

To explore anatomical landmark guided TAP, block as well as effect of mgso₄ as adjuvant to LA for post operative analgesia.

OBSERVATIONS & RESULTS:

Mgso₄ in TAP block provided better sensorimotor blockage, & prolonged Postoperative analgesia then Local anaesthetic agent alone.

CONCLUSION:

Mgso₄ is good adjuvant to LA in anatomical landmark guided double TAP block, it provides prolonged postoperative analgesia.

KEY WORDS:

Mgso₄, Anatomical landmark guided TAP block, open hernia repair, geriatric patients.

INTRODUCTION

Inguinal hernia repair surgery is one of the commonest surgery in male geriatric patients . (1) multimodal Anaesthesia techniques can be done like general anaesthesia (GA), neuraxial anaesthesia (spinal or epidural) or peripheral nerve blocks and TAP block. Geriatric patients have poor cardiorespiratory reserves so general anaesthesia may not be a good option for inguinal hernia repair surgery because it affects cardiopulmonary functions the most.

Neuraxial anaesthesia (spinal or epidural anaesthesia) is an attractive choice But in geriatric patients hypotension and other hemodynamic changes are often observed as autonomic nervous system response is diminished with aging and sympathetic block with epidural anaesthesia cannot be controlled (2).

Cardiovascular system may be profoundly affected by spinal anaesthesia due to unavoidable sympathetic blockade. Hypotension is the most frequent side effect of spinal anaesthesia, occurring in more than 30% of patients (3). In conventional spinal anaesthesia it is not possible to limit the accompanied sympathetic block that normally exceeds the sensory block by 2-6 segments (4, 5). **Ward et al** (6) reported a decrease in mean arterial blood pressure of 21.3% of the base line following spinal anaesthesia.

The Transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block is a relatively new regional anaesthesia technique that provides analgesia to the parietal peritoneum as well as the skin and muscles of the anterior abdominal wall (8). It has a high margin of safety and is technically simple to perform, especially under ultrasound guidance. TAP block can preserve bladder and lower limb motor function thereby assisting early mobilization after surgery. Historically described just a decade ago, it has undergone several modifications, which have highlighted its potential utility

for an increasing array of surgical procedures (9). Despite a relatively low risk of complications and a high success rate using modern ultrasound guided techniques, TAP blocks can be good alternative to spinal anaesthesia (10).

Mgso4 is NMDA antagonist. It modulates pain at dorsal horn level when given intrathecal.(23) mgso4 is good adjuvant to Local Anaesthetic agent in peripheral nerve blocks(25)

This study was undertaken to compare the safety and efficacy of Mgso4 with Placebo (NS) as adjuvant to LA in anatomical landmark guided TAP block for unilateral hernia repair.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was a comparative observational study, after a written informed consent from all the patients. Present study was of elective 60 adult male patients of Geriatric age group having American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) grade I, II, & III divided randomly into two groups of 30 each (using randomised sealed opaque envelope) They were given Ultrasound guided TAP block with or without Mgso4 in unilateral fully reducible indirect inguinal hernia repair surgery with mesh repair.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

patients who did those not give consent, those with known hypersensitivity to local anaesthetic drugs, patients having bleeding disorders, untreated or uncontrolled co-morbidities like diabetic mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, morbid obesity and chronic renal failure, those with infection at the site of injection, patients with psychiatric disorders, and metabolic diseases.

Routine investigations like complete blood counts, urine examination, bleeding time, clotting time, chest x-ray PA view, electrocardiogram and other relevant investigations were done in all patients pre-operatively.

Group allocation:

Randomisation was done by Randomisation table.(26) Randomised Group allocation was done by sealed opaque envelope method.

Execution of sealed opaque envelope was opened just before the time of giving TAP block.

Sample size calculation:

Sample size was calculated on base of VAS as primary assuming standard deviations (SD) of 0.1 cm, minimum needed sample size to detect difference of 0.1 cm on VAS of 10 cm with alpha error of 0.05 & power of 80%, sample size was 27 in each group. We have enrolled 30 patients in each group.

Group- T patients received anatomical landmark guided (USG) Transversus abdominis plane block (TAPB) with 30ml of 0.375% isobaric bupivacaine, and isobaric lignocaine 1.5% 10 ml on the side of hernia repair with 1 ml Normal Saline .

Group- TM patients received same LA with 150mg of 50% Mgso4 (0.3 ml) in NS to make 1ml volume. 0.3 ml volume was taken by insulin syringe (12 marks of syringe).The same anesthetist performed all procedures in both groups. **Preoperative preparation:**

The patients were assessed thoroughly in the preoperative room with Nil by mouth of 6 hours a good IV access was secured and intravenous fluid (ringer lactate) started at 10 ml/kg.

Thereafter, patients were shifted to operation theater and all standard monitoring devices were attached which included noninvasive blood pressure, Heart Rate, respiratory rate and SpO2. Anaesthesia workstation was prepared e cardiopulmonary Resuscitation, all emergency drugs were kept ready. All patients were connected to venturimask and were given oxygen @ 4 litres/ min throughout the intraoperative procedure. Each patient was premedicated with intravenous ondansatrom 0.04mg/kg in the operating room before the procedure.

patients were placed in supine position on Operation table. After draping and taking all aseptic precautions on the side of operation, unilateral TAP block was given through triangle

of Petit, & loss of resistance was felt by 2 pops off & study drug was given according to group allocation.

(A successful block means a sensory block of unilateral T10 to L1 dermatomes by 30 minutes, after which it was considered as a failure and patient was given GA).

Time of onset and time taken to achieve highest dermatomal level of sensory block was recorded. motor block was assessed by modified bromage scale.

Patients with inadequate block were also converted to GA and excluded from study.

Heart rate, continuous ECG, blood pressure and SpO₂ were monitored and recordings were taken preoperatively, at 5 minutes intervals initially for 20 minutes, at 30 minutes, at 45 minutes, at 60 minutes and post-operatively.

Patients were watched for Perioperative Adverse effects like nausea, vomiting, bradycardia, hypotension, altered sensorium or seizure episodes due to inadvertent intravascular injection of Local anaesthetic agent, Visceral perforation, intraperitoneal injection, bowel perforation were recorded & if occurred treated accordingly .

- Hypotension was defined as decrease in systolic blood pressure greater than 20% from baseline, & was treated with ephedrine 6 mg IV bolus and was repeated if required.

- Bradycardia was defined as Heart rate less than 60 beats per minute & was treated with 0.3-0.6 mg of atropine IV bolus.

The quality of block was assessed according to the following scale:

• Numeric Scale for Quality of Block:

Grade IV: (Excellent) No complaint from patient.

Grade III: (Good) Minor complaint with no need for the supplemental analgesics.

Grade II: (Moderate) Complaint that required supplemental analgesia.

Grade I: (Unsuccessful) Patient given general anaesthesia.

Intermittent bolus of 25-50 mcg of fentanyl was given intravenously to patients who needed Perioperative supplemental analgesics, as no motor blockage was there due to TAP block. All patients were observed in postoperative recovery room for duration of analgesia, time to first rescue analgesic requirement and total analgesic consumption in 24 hours. The patients were assessed for pain, based on Visual Analogue scale (VAS). The patients were explained about VAS in detail.

Post operative analgesia

Inj. Tramadol 50 mg intravenous was used as a rescue analgesic in patients who had VAS score >3 postoperatively.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Comparability of the groups was analyzed by student's t test. For intragroup comparison paired 't' test was used and for intergroup comparison unpaired 't' test was used. we used a sample size of total 60 patients (30 in each group). For all statistical analysis, the value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant and value of $p < 0.001$ was considered highly significant. All statistical tests were done using SPSS software version 16.0). Data was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The various observations noted included time of onset of sensory block, time to reach maximum/highest level of sensory block, motor block (modified bromage scale), duration of surgery, VAS postoperatively at 4 hourly intervals upto first 24 hours, time taken for first rescue analgesia postoperatively (duration of analgesia) and total analgesic consumption in first 24 hours, quality of block, and incidence of any adverse effects (eg- bradycardia, hypotension, nausea, vomiting, headache, bowel perforation, bladder retention etc)

OBSERVATIONS & RESULTS:

The baseline demographic parameters were statistically comparable in both groups (Table 1). The intraoperative hemodynamic parameters were comparable regarding Heart rate (HR), but

SBP, DBP and MBP were comparable. 3patients had hypotension and 2 patients had Bradycardia in Group TM while no complications were seen in Group T.

TABLE 1 DEMOGRAPHICS

PARAMETERS	GROUP T	GROUP TM	P value	Infernce
(MEAN+/- SD)	(MEAN±SD)	(MEAN±SD)		
AGE (YEARS)	1. 64.4±4.7	69.85±6.14	>0.05	NS
HEIGHT (CM)	156.0±3.2	155.8±3.1	>0.05	NS
WEIGHT(KG)	61.45±5.3	62.5±6.86	>0.05	NS
ASA grade (I/II/III)	18/8/4	20/7/3	>0.05	NS
DURATION OF SURGERY (MIN)	60.24±6.2	60.82±6.51	>0.05	NS

TABLE 2 :COMPARISON OF SENSORIMOTOR BLOCKAGE CHARACTERISTICS AND USAGE OF ANALGESIC SUPPLEMENTATION

PARAMETER	GROUP T (N=30)	GROUP TM (N=30)	p VALUE	INFERENCE
Time needed to perform block (mins)	15.22±1.55	14.20±0.52	> 0.05	NS
Time needed for maximum level of sensory block	28.0±1.29	26.68±0.74	>0.05	NS
Modified bromage score (3/2/1/0)	0/0/0/30	0/0/1/29	>0.05	NS
Perioperative fentanyl consumption(in mcg)	175+/-25	100+/-25	<0.05	S

Time taken for first analgesia	941.0±23.18	1340.25±5.44	< 0.001	HS
Postop Total rescue analgesia (inj Tramadol in mg)	107.5±24.5	50±10.5	< 0.001	HS
VAS in 24 hrs	4+/-1.5	2.9+/-1.2	<0.05	S

T. There was significantly lower VAS scores in Group TM and the duration of post operative analgesia was significantly higher in Group T (Table 2). The total dose of rescue analgesic required in Group T was significantly less (Table 2). The total fentanyl consumption was higher in Group T. a significantly higher number of patients in Group T had lower bromage scores (Table 2).

TABLE 3

QUALITY OF BLOCKAGE IN BOTH GROUPS

GRADE	GROUP T(%)	GROUP TM(%)
4	0 (0%)	0(0.%)
3	9 (30.0%)	10(31.7%)
2	21 (70.0%)	20(68.3%)
1	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)

GRADE4: EXCELLENT

GRADE 3: GOOD

GRADE2:MODERATE

GRADE1: FAILED

- * Preoperative Haemodynamics were comparable & with in normal limits (no change more than 20%of baseline values)
- * No Patient have any adverse reactions or complications.HR was slightly increased post procedure in both groups,it may be due to anxiety.but return to baselune value after 20 to 25 mins when effect of block established.

- * Mean VAS SCORE in first 24 hours were less in TM group (T group it was 4+/-1.5, in TM group 2.9+/-1.2).
- * Total requirements of Perioperative analgesic (inj fentanyl IV) was less in TM group (In T group it was 175+/-25mcg, in TM group it was 100+/-25mcg). postoperative analgesia in 24 hrs (Tramadol consumption) was also less in TM group.
- * 24 hrs low VAS & low Total Analgesia consumption in 24 hrs in group TM shows profound analgesia by mgso4.

DISCUSSION:

Transverse abdominis plane (TAP) block is a holy grail of regional anaesthesia technique that provides analgesia following abdominal surgery. TAP block significantly reduces pain associated with lower abdominal surgery, regardless of whether it is used as sole anaesthetic or for postoperative analgesia

Minimal haemodynamic changes following this technique is observed. The present study was carried with the aim of establishing the efficacy and safety of TAP block with or without Mgso4 as adjuvant.

The **Demographic data** of the patients in both groups (table 1) were comparable. The duration of surgical procedure was also comparable in both groups. The Duration, required to perform block (table 2) was found to be non significant ($p > 0.05$). The Time to highest/maximum level of sensory block (table 2) was comparable in both groups.

* **Sensorimotor blockage characteristics:**

Shibata et al (2007) assessed the extent of ultrasound guided TAP block by pinprick method & found that the mean upper and lower level of sensory block at 30 min after local anesthetic injection were T10 (range, T9–11) and L1 (range, T12–L1), respectively (11). In group T of our study the time to reach the maximum level of sensory block was 28 ± 1.29 min. Thus the results in our study was comparable to the above study. There was no motor blockade in group T whereas 1 patient of group TM had grade 1 motor block (table 2), a non significant difference ($p > 0.05$). **Zorica Jankovic et al (2009)** also found that there are no motor deficiency in TAP block (14).

* **Haemodynamic changes:**

In group-T & In group-TM the heart rate was lower compared to their pre-procedure value at all time interval measured. Heart rate then returned to pre-procedure values after 20 minutes.

Casati et al 1999 (17), Showed TAP block provides better stable hemodynamic profile.

In group-T & TM there were no significant changes in the systolic, diastolic and mean blood pressures (SBP, DBP, MAP) compared to their Baseline value. In the study of Sulagna

Bhattacharjee et al (20) systolic and diastolic BP were significantly higher in Group N (TAP block with normal saline followed by general anaesthesia) in comparison to group B (TAP block with 0.25% Bupivacaine followed by general anaesthesia) (15).

K. O Connor et al (2010) reported that there is no haemodynamic sequelae of neuraxial sympathectomy in TAP block as in neuraxial block (16).

* The duration of analgesia (the time taken for first rescue analgesic) (table 2) was less in group-T (941.0 ± 235.18 min) as compared to group-TM (1340.25 ± 5.44 min). The mean VAS immediately after surgery was more in group-T (2.8 ± 0.55) in comparison to group-TM (0.2 ± 0.32) (highly significant, $p < 0.001$). The mean VAS afterwards was more in group-T in comparison to group-TM. The finding of prolonged postoperative analgesia after TAPB is similar to studies by other authors.

Iyad Abbas Salman et al (2012) have observed that traditional treatment had better pain control in 1st 2 hours whereas TAP block was better thereafter (18).

In the study of Davarci et al the VAS score was <1 up to 90 minute and increased gradually to 1, 3, 3 at 2, 4 and 6 hour respectively and then decreased to 1.5 at 24 hours, in their USA group (unilateral spinal anaesthesia with Bupivacaine alone) (13).

* The quality of block (table 4) was better in group-TM in comparison to group-T. As TAP block have no effect on visceral pain, hence quality of block were poorer in TAP group but additional adjuvant Mgso4. Improve the quality of block.

* Comparing the side effects and complications in both groups, both groups were comparable ($p>0.05$). **Karim Mukhtar et al** (2009) stated that TAP block have high margin of safety, There have been no reported complications.

Shelly Rana et al (24) used 150 mg Mgso4 in USG guided TAP block. they also noticed prolonged postoperative analgesia & Haemodynamic stability same as our study.

CONCLUSION:

In nutshell 150 mg Mgso4 is good adjuvant to LA in anatomical landmark guided TAP block for inguinal hernia repair in geriatric patients in terms of prolonged post operative analgesia, excellent hemodynamic stability with minimal incidence of adverse effects.

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